

INCLUSIVE PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH AND CLASSROOM INSTRUCTION IN A HOME-BASED LEARNING MODE FOR PUBLIC SCHOOLS

MARY JANE B. ALVERO

maryjane.alvero@deped.gov.ph

0000-0003-1462-3973

San Lucas 1 Elementary School, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines
Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was teachers' perceptions of inclusive pedagogical approach and classroom instruction as to learning outcome and effective instruction as well as their readiness and needs for professional learning in order to work with diverse learners and looked at teachers' perceptions of the model's outcomes and gives voice to teachers who work in challenging, diverse classrooms about the barriers to inclusive practice. The study's research questions focused on teachers' effective instruction and preferred mode of professional learning. In line of this, this study aims to determine the significant relationship of between the perceived inclusive pedagogical approaches and classroom instruction as to learning outcome and effective instruction. The researcher used Universal Design for Learning Model the multiple means of engagement, multiple means of representation and multiple means of action and expression. The conceptual framework for this research consisted of design for learning and socio-emotional learning. The use of descriptive and correlational research design-led in achieving the objectives of the study participated by 5 schools and 129 teachers from the Schools Division of San Pablo City. The result showed that inclusive pedagogical approach as to design for learning and socio-emotional learning was significant as to learning outcome and effective instruction a positive significant relationship was manifested. The study's findings may provide on how to build teachers' capacity to create classrooms where all learners can succeed while reducing reliance on separate diverse learners. By encouraging respect and empathy among pupils to work together and celebrate their collective successes, this could help promote social change in the school culture.

Keyword: Inclusive Pedagogical Approach, Design for Learning, Socio-Emotional Learning, Classroom Instruction, Learning Outcome, Effective Instruction